

Peace Building Through Religious Education: A Post-Communist Country Perspective

Genti Kruja

Article Info

Article History

Received:
July 05, 2024

Accepted:
October 06, 2024

Keywords :

Religious Education,
Inter-Religious Dialogue,
Multi-Religious Society,
Peace Building, Albania

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13895882

Abstract

Public awareness on perceiving religious dialogue as a determinant of conflict prevention and social peace building in intercultural and multi-religious societies is increasing day by day. For a long time, the debate over religion was characterized by the idea that the increasing secularism of Western societies would lead to a gradual withdrawal of religion from public space. However, the last decade, returned religion in public discussion as a determinant of peace building. Regardless of the variety of how this discussion unfolds in European countries, the study of the impact of "religion" on intercultural dialogue and on tensions and social conflicts seems to be becoming increasingly important. Meanwhile education and religious education is an important element for shaping the critical skills of future citizens, for intercultural dialogue and for peace building as well.

This research focuses on assessing the peace building contribution of religious education in Albaniaa multi religious society, in two different periods of time, the pre-communist era and the post-communist regime. An explorative research methodology is implemented to achieve this aim through collecting primary and secondary data. Documents and studies in the field of religious education were collected from Central State Archive for the pre-communist period and data from the current schools of different religious communities in Albania were evaluated.

The study brings to attention the Albanian case, where religious education had in the past and has currently a decisive impact on peace building. Religious communities have dozens of schools and 4 universities, where thousands of students' study and their graduates constitute a vital part of the society. Education plays an essential role in intercultural understanding, in favour of coexistence and tolerance and the contribution of these schools to society is enormous asthey are strengthening interfaith dialogue and its transmission to young people. In addition to the collaboration between the three theologies, cooperation is also increasing between universities, which despite being founded by religious communities, have in general and other secular departments of various academic fields.

Introduction

The evolution of the religious phenomenon in Albania can be summed up in a single phrase; religion has passed from being to not be and again to being. In all three of these moments, religion has tended to self-define its identity through a difficult movement, especially in the Balkan terrain, where political tensions and nationalist mentalities have been and remain strong (Sinani, 2017, p. 6).

In the Middle Ages, the church was divided into Roman Catholic and Byzantine Orthodox. This phenomenon divided the Albanians into two religious' denominations. After the sixteenth century, The Islam began to spread rapidly under the Ottoman rule. Today there are five religious communities recognized by the Albanian state with a special agreement, the Albanian Muslim Community, the Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Albania, the Catholic Church, the Bektashi Community and the Evangelical Brotherhood of Albania.

In the League of Nations, Albanian Prime Minister Iljaz Vrioni emphasized that: "Freedom of conscience and religion prevailed and all Albanian citizens freely enjoyed the same political and social rights regardless of religion (AMPJ, 1921, p. 20)." Since 1923, Albania has been the only country in Europe that drafts legal norms for the granting of legal personality to religious communities, which represents the most advanced degree of elaboration of European law, proving its ability to engage substantially in constructive debate, so necessary for the establishment of the modern state (Cimbalo, 2013, p. 43). Albania does not recognize victims of religious intolerance. Furthermore, Albanian Muslims sheltered 3,000 Jewish during World War.

After World War II, religion suffered a hard hit that led to its official ban in 1967. Prohibition of religion by law does not mean that it was finally liquidated while many believers practiced religious rites secretly at home (Sinani, 2017, p. 8). For many decades, Albania lived under a strict communist regime, lacking much freedom and human rights. Some freedoms, such as freedom of religion, were completely forbidden. Many religious leaders were prosecuted; hundreds of churches and mosques were destroyed; religious names were almost impossible to use for new-born babies. In conditions of a long absence of freedom of religion and when cultural life was monocultural, and the value system was commanded and controlled by a highly elaborate structure, the transition to a new stage of society could not be accompanied by some kind of crisis in the value system, including moral values. Communism promised people a paradise on earth. The Saviour was the Communist Party. The deeds of the communist leader were replaced by the Holy Books. The blow to religion did indeed destroy religion from an institutional point of view, but in a sense strengthened religious sentiment.

All this changed only with the fall of the communist regime and with the advent of democracy and political pluralism in the 1990s. As a very important cultural element, religion in Albania has a great role to play in cultivating values that respect the world vision of every culture and religion. Recognition, cooperation and religious tolerance in Albania constitute an imperative for Albanian society (Sinani, 2017, p. 9).

Interfaith dialogue and co-existence are a challenging mission. In recent years, Albanian state have been trying to move forward, playing an active role in keeping interfaith coexistence healthy. One of these steps has been the opening of Islamic, Orthodox and Catholic theological programs in Albania so that religious leaders and experts can be educated and trained within Albania. Another important project of the Albanian state has been the idea to include a course on religion, where dialogue in high and high schools aims to support, maintain, and maintain healthy harmony between the various religious communities in the country and to provide a good example for others.

Sinani (2017), reports a statement of Barrije: "Albania has witnessed a very rare religious tolerance and will remain one of the permanent features of its history, whether protagonists (p. 12-13)." Albanian Muslims and Christians are an example and a symbol of religious harmony in the history of Balkan nations and beyond. They have always lived in harmony and have coexisted without divisive confrontations among them; instead, they have been complementary to each other. The existence of churches and mosques close to each other proves the interfaith co-existence among Albanians.

Leaders of all religious communities have already created the Inter-religious Council. This joint forum plans to meet periodically, in which a consistent message of peace and harmony between believers of all communities would be articulated, and their work and activities on behalf of co-existence and common future will be coordinated. Currently, five different religious communities in Albania are members of the Interreligious Council of Albania (IRCA), which was established in 2007 (Kruja, 2020, p. 77).

This research focuses on assessing the peace building contribution of religious education in Albania, a multi religious society, in two different periods of time, the pre-communist era and the post-communist regime. An explorative research methodology is implemented to achieve this aim through collecting primary and secondary data. Documents and studies in the field of religious education were collected from Central State Archive for the pre-communist period and data from the current schools of different religious communities in Albania were evaluated.

Overview of Religious Education in Albania

With the declaration of Albania's independence in 1912 and the establishment of the independent Albanian state, the improvement of education became a major concern for the new country. In the newspaper of the Vlora Government at that time was stated: "Only with sound ploughing and real education can our nation be revived and transformed and can gain the right to enter the ranks of civilized peoples" (Bello, 2012, p. 66). According to the opportunities available, the Ministry of Education in the school year 1913-1914 opened 46 primary schools and two normal preparatory schools for the vacant areas (Shaplllo, 1966, p. 94). In the context of strengthening national unity, the First Government sought to pursue a balanced policy of rapprochement with all religious beliefs. This is also illustrated by the fact that some well-known clergymen of that time held key positions in government.

World War I constitute one of the most complicated periods in the history of Albania. The territory of our country became a battleground for both warring blocs. In 1916 Albania was divided into three occupation zones, Austro-Hungarian, Italian and French. Within its strategic interests to strengthen the Albanian element, the Austro-Hungarian Military Command, which had occupied part of Albania, took steps to establish a local administration by establishing three directorates: Directorate General of Education, Directorate of Finance and the Directorate of Justice. It is noteworthy that during this period many Albanian schools were opened and some of the main programs for the history of the Albanian school and pedagogical thought were developed. During this period, all religious schools opened a religious subject prepared and taught by the religious communities. According to the syllabus this course occupied three hours per week for the first three years and two hours per week for the fourth and fifth year (Hoti, 2002, p. 201).

After the end of World War I, in 1920, the Lushnja Education Congress decided that the religious education programs and classes were to be left to the authorities of each religion, with the Ministry of Education having the right to control these classes. Despite these concessions, the new Albanian state adopted no official religion and declared that it pursued a secular policy in its relations with the communities and religious practices of the population. This was done to strengthen the national bond between the Albanians of the three religious' faiths. Consequently, the secular state proclaimed itself the acting agent of the nation, and in the name of national unity, it exercised strict control over religious affairs and organizations (Clayer, 2010, p. 1).

With the advent of the communist regime in 1944, persecution of religions began, and all religious schools were closed. After a certain period, religious classes in state schools started to be reduced up to their closure.

Nowadays there are around 3,000 public schools, around 400 private schools, 4 Madrasahs (Islamic schools), 57 Catholic schools and 30 Orthodox schools in Albania. Number of students in Madrasahs and Bedër University is around 3,000 students. There are around 10,000 students in Catholic schools and around 3,000 students in Orthodox schools. Meanwhile the number of students of three theologies is about 200 graduate and ongoing students at the department of Islamic Sciences, 343 in Orthodox theology and 133 in Catholic theology. Currently the Albanian government has started a pilot project in five public schools in Tirana, where it has introduced the course of "religious culture". However, there has been a lot of controversy over this.

Islamic Education

The madrasahs in Albania have a centuries-old tradition, founded after the acceptance of Islam by Albanians in the 14th century. Madrasahs continued their function even after the declaration of independence in 1912, but were faced with economic, didactic, and educational difficulties, without central control (Kruja, et al., 2017, p. 1). In 1923 the Albanian Muslim Community was established in Tirana, as the only official institution of Islamic religious life in Albania. Due to the new developments of the 20th century, a new kind of madrasah was needed, which would be adapted to a new model. In 1924, the High Madrasah was opened in Tirana, which would later end in closing all existing ones in other cities.

Immediately after the installation of Communism in Albania in 1944, pressure and persecution on religious leaders began, with many arrests and imprisonment of Tirana's madrasah teachers. Continuing the process of education under difficult conditions, in 1964, the madrasah was finally closed. Meanwhile, in 1967, law banned all religious denominations.

With the change of the political system in Albania after the 1990s, one of the major freedoms brought by the new democratic system was the freedom of religion, which has carried the path of democracy forward since November 1990. The Muslim community, which closed in 1967, reopened once again to continue its operations in 1991 (Zaimi and Kruja, 2014, p. 9).

Today we see that at the heart of all global problems lies the human factor. So all problems start in man and end with him. Thus, for a functional social order, the most effective form is education. Education through learning and teaching are also referred to as two divine missions. In the philosophy of madrasahs, the school is the place where teaching and education are taught. School is the institution that sheds light on life events and gives students the opportunity to understand what is happening around them. As a school concept, Madrasah in Albania is the place where faith and science are together. Thus, the madrasah education system has reunited the contemporary educational system with the classical madrasah system (Kutlu, 2016, p. 58).

Meanwhile teachers have a great value in society. The teacher is a perfect guide that shapes all human life. The influence of the teacher on the individual is much greater than the influence of the parents or society (Kruja, 2014, p. 57). In the philosophy of madrasahs, the teacher is very important because he prepares the individual and the society of the future. The disruption of the education system first affected teachers. As they lost their social quality and influence, so did the quality of people. And in fact, teachers are both conductors of the values of a virtuous society, and examples of pious individuals who aspire to dialogue and tolerance.

The teacher in general, be it the mother, father, or elders, the teacher through concepts, or through examples, is precisely the helper, which helps one to perceive correctly and thus overcome misperceptions. Education is the only process of salvation, because even under the Socratic formula, "knowledge is a virtue" (Faruki, 2009, p. 48). In the philosophy of madrasahs, the teacher from birth to death is a blessed master who gives life to the world through shaping the lives of people. Moreover, in fact, teachers' influence over individuals far outweighs the influence of parents and society on them. The teacher is the one who cooks for the mother, father, and all members of the society of the future. If he is not involved in cooking any part of the individual's dough, then that individual remains unformed throughout his life (Kruja, 2014, p. 61).

In 2011, the Muslim Community of Albania established Bedër College University, which includes the Department of Islamic Sciences at the Faculty of Humanities. The mission of the Department of Islamic Sciences at Bedër University is to provide education in full compliance with international standards, along with its contribution to society. To accomplish this mission, the Department of Islamic Sciences, in addition to

developing its academic program, has carried out various activities in the field of teaching, research and contributing to social benefits.

Bedër operates on a non-profit basis and supports successful students who wish to pursue academic studies. The Department of Islamic Sciences aims to help students acquire the skills of reading and evaluating the classical and contemporary sources of Islamic Studies by educating students in a way that they acquire deep knowledge of religious and social aspects in line with the field of study. Islam, as well as their preparation and shaping through intertwining of tradition, culture and contemporary reality.

Students who graduate from the Department of Islamic Sciences have employment opportunities, first, in all institutions of the Albanian Muslim Community. Second, students who graduate from the Department of Islamic Science can be employed as teachers in madrasas. Another job opportunity is as an assistant or lecturer in Bedër. From 2014 until now, about 200 students have graduated or continue their studies at the Department of Islamic Sciences. Since its establishment College University Bedër has given special importance to the organization of various academic activities of interfaith dialogue.

At the same time Bedër University in cooperation with the Muslim Community of Albania have trained more than 600 imams from all over Albania. The coaches were from the academic staff of Bedër University, and often invited leaders of the Muslim community, as well as Islamic personalities from Albania and the Islamic world.

Albania's Muslim Community, Bedër University College and the Madrasahs are currently the voice of Islam's moderation, as well as a positive model and example of autochthonous Islam in the region and Europe and are consistent with EU principles. In addition to the traditional Islamic theological courses, such modern courses as Sociology, Psychology, Philosophy, History, History of Religions, comparative studies of religions and interfaith dialogue are also given.

Christian Education

Orthodox Education

Despite the many, often speculative discussions, the current religious situation in Albania is a historical result and as such requires adjustment based on religious tolerance. The 19th century is the century of awakening of the Balkan peoples, when under the influence of new ideas, they began to move to gain their freedom. Along with national movements, there was, of course, the desire to create national churches (Sinani, 2017, p. 6).

The movement for the independence of the Albanian Orthodox Church dates back to the 17th century. This movement first appeared in the form of trying to use the Albanian language in various religious services in the church. In 1909 the "Orthodox League" was created in Korça, which aimed to achieve the knowledge of the Albanian language among churches for services and prayers.

From the beginning of 1921, the Albanian Orthodox clergy started work for the Autocephalous Church in Albania. By now, the mass in the Albanian language was gradually gaining wide popularity. It extended from the Durres Orthodox Churches of Tirana to Korça and Gjirokastra. In 1921, the Korça Orthodox, through a request sent to the government authorities, raised the need to solve the problem of ordination in the Albanian language, calling it a vital issue for the Albanian Orthodox (AQSH, 1921, p. 29).

On September 12, 1922, the Congress of Berat was called, with representatives from all Albanian Orthodox communities, under the leadership of Josif Qiric (Sinani, 2017, p. 7). In addition to the main decision proclaiming the Albanian Orthodox Church as Autocephalous, the Statute of the National Orthodox Church of Albania was drafted and approved in Congress (Sinani, 2017, p. 7). This congress declared the administrative independence of the Albanian Orthodox Church even de jure, because de facto it existed, since the declaration of political independence of the Albanian state in 1912. According to this statute, the supreme authority of the church, until the episcopal synod was formed, was the High Council of four clergy. This Council was also tasked by Congress to enter into an agreement with the Ecumenical Patriarchate on official recognition of independence. The Synod elected Christopher of Korca, who in March 1937 left for Istanbul to recognize the church and the Patriarchate was forced to recognize the independence of the church in April 1937 (Sinani, 2017, p. 7).

In 1930 the Orthodox Church opened a seminary for the formation of clergy in Durres and continued its activity until 1944, when the communist regime was installed in Albania. Another seminar was opened in Korça in 1937, which functioned until 1941.

After the fall of the communist regime, the Orthodox Church Seminary was opened, which in the 1998-1999 academic year rose to the level of a theological academy (Beduli, 2001, p. 5-6).

The Orthodox Theological Academy since 2017 is part of the University College "Logos", founded by the Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Albania and is officially recognized as a "Bachelor" study program in "Studies in Social Theology & Religious Sciences". There are 321 graduate students from Orthodox Theological Academy and 22 students on going in the new Department. In addition to theological studies, the Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Albania has a network of elementary and secondary schools in several cities of Albania.

Catholic Education

After the proclamation of independence, the Albanian government recognized the Catholic religion, with all its rites, "free exercise throughout the Albanian state," and the dependence of the heads of various dioceses on ecclesiastical matters only from the Holy See. The Statute and the Concordat contained other articles, which touched on many aspects ... Likewise, Article 7 stated: "The clergy have freedom of speech and of the press, dogmatically, morally and apologetically enough not to use offensive forms against other religions." Although this concordat was not realized, for certain political reasons, it proves a modern legal tradition. Following the fall of the totalitarian regime, the Vatican and the Albanian government ratified in 2011 (Sinani, 2017, p. 7-8).

In formal pre-university education, 8,000 students attend Catholic educational institutions. The Catholic Church of Albania also has 34 kindergartens and day care centres, 13 elementary schools, 5 high schools, 7 vocational training centres, Catholic University "Our Lady of Good Counsel" and dozens of social and cultural centres for children.

In terms of impact nationally the share of Catholic institutions varies from 2% in pre-primary, basic and secondary education up to 20% in vocational education. The number of Catholic preschools accounts for 1.6% of Catholic institutions nationally, while Catholic institutions for primary and secondary education make up less than 1% nationwide. Also, in terms of the number of children, about 8,224 (2.3% of children nationally) are educated at Catholic institutions and only 1% of students attending primary and secondary education attend Catholic institutions (Zahaj & Sula, 2017, p. 29).

In terms of comparing Catholic institutions with private education throughout the country, their impact is even greater. The share of Catholic institutions varies from 4% in secondary education, 15% in basic education, and 18% in secondary education up to 100% in vocational education. Data reported by the Albanian Ministry of Education show that there is no private school to provide vocational education. Regarding the number of children, about 9% of students in secondary education attend Catholic education, 17% in basic education and 27% in preschool.

Regarding the number of children, about 9% of students in secondary education attend Catholic education, 17% in basic education and 27% in preschool. Data over the years show that 48% of students are Catholic. Since there are no religious subjects in Catholic schools, these schools are also frequented by children of other faiths, especially children of needy families, those with a single parent, etc. (Zahaj & Sula, 2017, p. 47).

Meanwhile the Catholic Theological Institute was opened in 1992. It is an institute, not a department of any university. There are 104 graduated students and 29 on going.*

Religious Education and Peace Building: Challenges and Perspectives

Albania is in a geographical and regional position, where there have been wars and various ethnic conflicts, but also on religious grounds. It is a multi-religious society and a Muslim majority country living in the European continent, a characteristic of importance mentioned by several political and religious world leaders on many occasions (Gjana, 2020). In the Balkans and now everywhere in the West, societies are multi-ethnic, multicultural, and multi-religious. In such polarized societies, building lasting peace through education and dialogue is very important.

For a long time, the debate over religion was characterized by the idea that the increasing secularism of Western societies would lead to a gradual withdrawal of religion from public space. But in the last decade, there has been a return to religion in public discussion. Regardless of the variety of how this discussion unfolds in European countries, the study of the impact of "religion" on intercultural dialogue and on tensions and social conflicts seems to be becoming increasingly important. There is a public awareness of seeing intercultural and religious dialogue as a factor in conflict prevention and strengthening social peace in a multi-religious society.

Since the aftermath of September 11, 2001, the dangers of religious isolation, confrontation, and instrumentalization of religion for political purposes have become a notable fact. However, religious values can serve to create a climate of peaceful coexistence between different religions and to respect the human dignity of others, regardless of their religious and political beliefs. This also requires engagement in intercultural and interfaith education. A low degree in religious education can significantly influence the instrumentalization of religious differences for the purposes of political mobilization.

Following the democratic changes, such a challenge has been posed to Albanian society as well. To deal with it, it is now becoming more and more necessary to know the European experience in religious education (Sinani, 2017, p. 4).

In Recommendation 1720, adopted on 4 October 2005, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe stated:

"Education is essential to combat ignorance, stereotypes and misunderstanding of religions. Governments should also do more to guarantee freedom of conscience and religious

*Data collected from Institute of Catholic Theology in Scutari.

expression, encourage religious instruction, promote interfaith dialogue, and promote cultural and social expression of religions.

The school is an important element for educating and shaping the critical skills of future citizens and for intercultural dialogue. It will lay the foundations of tolerant behaviour based on respect for the dignity of every human being. The school will need to teach students the history and philosophy of all major religions in a thoughtful and objective manner, while respecting the values of the European Convention on Human Rights.” (Sinani, 2017, p. 18)

Education is not about faith or unbelief, but about the basics of faith or unbelief. Objections to religious instruction focus on the practical difficulties that arise from the level of teacher preparation and the lack of didactic material. Another counter argument argues that for a professor to speak about religions he/she must not only know them in depth but also know the language of a particular religion. The fear on the part of the laity and the free mind is that through religious education at school we do not fall into catechism. In daily life, publications and charlatans are being swallowed up, which are said to be in contact with God, spreading a wave of irrationalism that drives the passions of people, especially the young. But even fundamentalists do not miss out on indoctrinating young people, who are not clear about the texts they refer (Sinani, 2017, p. 29).

The European experience to date attests to the evolution of religious teaching. This lesson exists but is developed under the influence of two factors; one is sociological, in the sense that the religious and philosophical pluralism of European societies compels them to include more religious and non-religious alternatives in the school curricula and secondly, a legal factor, through the importance of the principle of non-discrimination on philosophical and religious grounds in international acts and especially in the European Convention on Human Rights. Educational and religious institutions should greatly promote a culture of interfaith and interethnic dialogue and tolerance (Kruja, 2020). A positive example is brought by Beljanski and Bukvić (2020) research on the education of tolerance in Bosnia and Serbia, where it is evidenced that some state universities included subjects of education and intercultural dialogue. Moreover, Shehi et al. (2018) found that social science programmes in Albania offer varying coverage of peace education topics which positively impacts their peace perception and behaviour. These examples remain few compared to the need for peace education and peace building especially in the Balkan region, where wars and conflicts have not been absent (Bakalar, 2018; Beljanski & Bukvić, 2020).

The school is an important element for educating and shaping the critical skills of future citizens and for intercultural dialogue. It will lay the foundations of tolerant behaviour based on respect for the dignity of every human being. The school will need to teach students the history and philosophy of all major religions in a thoughtful and objective manner, respecting the values of the European Convention on Human Rights and effectively fighting bigotry... (Sinani, 2017, p. 18).

Religious education can be understood in the context of civic education, but religious education is not the same as civic education. There are two things to agree on between them at the European level; Religious education should be seen as a complement to civic education, which has the potential to incorporate global and European ideas of citizenship and to assist in school debate on issues related to pluralistic society. Religious education, in the form of interfaith education, can contribute to intercultural understanding as well as to tolerance and social harmony (Kruja, et al., 2017, p. 5).

The place of religion and the role of religious communities in social life can be understood through three examples: the legal foundations of the educational system, pluralism of teaching and religious instruction in public schools. Therefore, education plays an essential role in intercultural understanding, in favour of coexistence and tolerance.

Article 2 of the First Additional Protocol to the European Declaration on Human Rights states, inter alia: “No one shall be denied the right to education. The State, in the exercise of its functions in the field of education, must respect the right of parents to provide education in accordance with their religious and philosophical beliefs (Kruja, et al., 2017, p. 17).”

The above principles and other important principles of religion, society and law are applied by the Madrasahs of the Muslim Community of Albania and Bedër University College. The madrasahs develop the official curriculum for pre-university education cycles, but also have the religion-oriented curriculum, which is also approved by the Ministry of Education (Kruja, et al., 2017, p. 13).

The common themes of religious subjects aim at civic education, such as: national identity, recognition of cultures and respect for them, coexistence in the community, respect for fundamental democratic values, common history and heritage, respect for the laws of the land where we live, human rights and responsibilities, awareness of the unity and diversity of European and worldwide culture, students' awareness of the negatives of xenophobia, violence, racism, aggressive nationalism and intolerance, overall cleanliness and environmental preservation, safety and to guarantee its stabilization in society, the right to information, the right to speech, etc., whose norms do not conflict with Islamic principles in general (Kruja, et al., 2017, p. 25).

The above elements are particularly important to regulate family relationships, where there have been problems and the number of cases of domestic violence has increased over the past decade. There have also been increased and exacerbated conflicts between parents and children, between brothers and sisters, and between brothers of different age groups. One factor that has fuelled such phenomena has been, and continues to be, the violence that has been emitted by television equipment, particularly feature film violence.

In a study on teaching in madrasas in Albania, 90.7% of parents of madrasa students sent students to this school for the safety that the school offers compared to other schools in the country and meanwhile 85.2% of parents rate madrasa education level as very high successful. It should be noted that more than 95% of high school graduates in madrasahs, about 500 students each year, continue their university studies within the country or abroad. The general and common themes of religious subjects in madrasas aim a civic education, whose norms do not conflict with Islamic principles. These elements are particularly important to regulate family relationships, where there have been problems and the number of cases of domestic violence has increased over the past decade. To find out how violent television films affect relationships between Albanian families of our day, we conducted a survey in 2012 with in Tirana's high schools, surveying 1244 students from different schools, among them the madrasa of Tirana (Dervishi and Kruja, 2012).

We have concluded that from dialogues with pupils, girls use the internet more for useful information, for their formation, so that to accomplish their home-works in different subjects that learn in school and to develop better communication models than others. On the other hand, boys use the internet more for information, so that to disappear the curiosity, but they do not socialize with the most likeable cultural norms for games or to make jokes with each-other.

Scholars have been noticed that in this psycho-cultural occurrence which is complex, the accountable relationship permeates actively on two sides, or as it is characterized differently in a circular way: from one side, the violent television movie views urge a part of the youth-group teenagers to be more violent in their models of behaviour and from the other hand, being intuitive of aggressive behaviour urges them to see more television programs with violent thinking (Wimmes and Dominieli, 1987, p. 537).

So, in Tirana's Madrasah is tremendously felt in a low level the specific weight of teenagers (around 12.0 per cent) in accordance with the high-school students who have conflicts with their mothers. The healthy moral and the religious spirit, that is changed and practiced from teachers and students of the Madrasah, serves as an important factor for the teenage socialization with the behaviour human models and the most generous ones, not only in respect to the mothers and other family members, but also with others. Dervishi and Kruja (2012) propose the element of sociable techniques that are realized towards the religious moral and discipline, to be practiced even in middle and public schools, so that to neutralize the television movies of violent acts, of the over-loaded acts with vulgarity.

Teaching about religions and beliefs must be taught in a way that is fair, accurate, and based on accurate knowledge. Students must learn about religions and beliefs in an environment that respects human rights, fundamental freedoms, and civic values (Kruja, 2014, p. 31).

Within this spirit are also the interfaith symposiums organized between the three theologies, where 10 symposiums have been organized so far, which took place in Islamic, Orthodox and Catholic academic institutions, an academic collaboration between Bedër University in general and the Department of Islamic Sciences in particular, which in an interfaith collaboration with the Orthodox Theological Academy (today the Department of Social Theology and Religious Studies at Logos University College) and the Catholic Philosophical and Theological Institute at the Interdisciplinary Seminar, Shkodra. In one of these symposiums in 2018, Muslim, Catholic, and Orthodox students gathered with their professors chose one representative of each religion and prayed for peace, prosperity, more love for society and each other to provide social well-being and happiness. These interfaith cooperation organizations and many other activities of this kind provide Bedër Collage University with a specific mission and contribution to social peace in Albania and beyond. These interfaith cooperations are guarantees of preserving, promoting, and strengthening the spirit of cooperation between the different, as a multicultural and multi-religious pluralism (Kruja, 2018, p. 110).

Thus, educational, and academic institutions are playing an important role in strengthening interfaith dialogue and its transmission to young people. Thanks to this model in Albania, some European universities are officially cooperating to take Albania as a model. Some examples are the master's program on Interfaith Dialogue of the University of San Marino in partnership with the Department of Islamic Sciences at Bedër University; the organization of international conferences between three universities of religious communities in Albania, in collaboration with the University of Vienna; the summer school of interfaith dialogue organized by Potsdam University in Albania, etc. (Kruja, 2020, p. 83).

Conclusions and Implications

Public awareness on perceiving religious dialogue as a determinant of conflict prevention and social peace building in intercultural and multi-religious societies is increasing day by day. For a long time, the debate over religion was characterized by the idea that the increasing secularism of Western societies would lead to a gradual withdrawal of religion from public space. However, the last decade, returned religion in public discussion as a determinant of peace building. Regardless of the variety of how this discussion unfolds in European countries, the study of the impact of "religion" on intercultural dialogue and on tensions and social conflicts seems to be becoming increasingly important. Meanwhile education and moreover religious education is an important element for shaping the critical skills of future citizens, for intercultural dialogue and for peace building as well.

The current study brings to attention the Albanian case, a post-communist country, with multireligious population, where religious education had in the past and has currently a decisive impact on peace building. Nowadays, religious communities in Albania have dozens of schools and 4 universities opened by them, where thousands of students' study. The contribution of these schools to society is enormous, while their graduates constitute a vital part of Albanian society, but not only. Interfaith dialogue existed throughout centuries as a moral value in the cultural history of Albania. The harsh periods of communist regime obliterated the religious values and shook their foundations. After the totalitarian regime, interfaith dialogue has been carried out by the cooperation of all religious communities and their educational institutions. Beside Bedër University, Catholic University and Logos University there is Nehemia University, opened by evangelicals. Currently, in addition to the collaboration between the three theologies, cooperation is also increasing between universities, which despite being founded by religious communities, have in general and other secular departments of various academic fields.

This research has contributions in the field of religious education and peace building. It adds value with this unique case, where the five religious' communities in the country devote through their educational institutions and through continuous collaboration among each other to peace building and harmony for centuries. Moreover, the study brings practical implications referring to policymakers, religious and educational institutions in Albania, Balkans, Western and Eastern countries. Governmental institutions should plan and build proper policies supporting and subsidizing religious institutions, their educational and interreligious activities. However, religious institutions should focus on promoting their interreligious collaboration through more mutual activities and educational programs. Furthermore, they may jointly organise summer and winter schools and even more organise them on a multi-country perspective.

References

- *Programa për shkollat fillore pesë klasësh*, 1928, Shtypshkronja "Teknike", Tirana.
- AQSH (1917). Document No. 39. Central State Archive of Albania.
- AQSH (1922). Document No. 181. Central State Archive of Albania.
- AMPJ (1921). Document No. 88. Foreign Affairs Archive of Albania.
- Bakalar, B. (2018). Book Review: Justice on both sides: Transforming education through restorative justice. *American Journal of Qualitative Research*, 2(2), 145-149.
- Balla, Xh.(2010). Haxhi H. Mahmud Dashi, jeta dhe vepra 1873-1961. West Print, Tirana.
- Basha, A. M. (2011). *Rrugëtimi i Fesë Islame në Shqipëri (1912-1967)*. Tirana.
- Beduli, K.(2001). *Shkollat teologjike-hieratike të Kishës Orthodhokse Autoqefale të Shqipërisë (ndihmesë për historikun e tyre)*, Tirana.
- Beljanski, M. & Bukvić, E. D. (2020). Comparative overview of the presence of intercultural education of teacher trainees in Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(3), 1–16. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/412>
- Bello, H.(2012). *Përpjekjet e klerit mysliman shqiptar për vendosjen e mësim-besimit në shkollat shtetërore përgjatë viteve 1920-1924*. Zani i Naltë, 1 (154), Tirana.
- Cimbalo, G.(2013). *Pluralizmi i besimit dhe komunitetet fetare në Shqipëri*, Naimi, Tirana.
- Clayer, N.(2010). *Adapting Islam to Europe: The Albanian Example*. <http://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/docs/00/57/87/57/PDF/clayer-adaptislam-final.pdf>.
- Dervishi, Z.& Kruja, G. (2012). *Një vështrim sociologjik mbi problemet familjare tek të rinjtë e shkollave të Tiranës*. Zani i Naltë, 2, Tirana.
- Faruki, I.(2009). *Islami dhe Krishtërimi, Konflikt apo Dialog*. Erasmus, Tirana.
- Gjana, F. (2020). *Interreligious dialogue and its contribution to international security: The case of Albania*. In *Paths to a culture of tolerance and peace*. River Publishers.
- Hoti, V.(2002). *Luigj Gurakuqi-për shkollën shqipe dhe arsimin kombëtar*, Camaj-Pipa, Scutari.
- Kruja, G., Skura, G. & Gjedia, R. (2017). *Të mësuarit e normave civile në medresetë e Shqipërisë*. AFALC, Tirana.
- Kruja, G.(2014). *Filozofia e medreseve në sistemin arsimor të Shqipërisë*. Zani i Naltë, 7 (160), Tirana.
- Kruja, G.(2018). *Albania, a model of interfaith harmony for Europe?* Tirana.

Kruja, G. (2020). Interfaith Dialogue in Albania as a Model of Interreligious Harmony. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(3), 76-87. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/377>

Kutlu, A.(2016). Perceptimi i prindërve lidhur me edukimin fetar në Shqipëri: rasti i medreseve. UET, Tirana.

Noli, F. S. (1988). ASHSH, 2, Tirana.

Shaplo, S. (1966). Lufta për shkollën kombëtare përgjatë viteve 1920-1924.in: *Mbi lëvizjen kombëtare dhe demokratike shqiptare në vitet 1918-1924*, Mihal Duri, Tirana.

Shehi, R. Z., Ozcan, S., & Hagen, T. (2018). The Role of Higher Education Institutions in Building a Culture of Peace: An Albanian Case. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development*, 13(1), 46-61.

Sinani, Gj. (2017). Feja dhe edukimi. Fondacioni “Friedrich Ebert”, Tirana

Zahaj, S.& Sula, G.(2017). Studimi i institucioneve arsimore parauniversitare katolike në Shqipëri: impakti, rëndësia dhe vlerat e shtuara. Qendra Botuese Shoqata e Jezuitëve, Tirana.

Zaimi, A.&Kruja, G. (2014).Katalog i Veprimtarisë së Komunitetit Mysliman të Shqipërisë, botimet KMSH, Tirana.

Webliography

https://www.riverpublishers.com/book_details.php?book_id=780

Author Information

Genti Kruja

University College Bedër, Tirana, Albania
